

Aquatic fungi and fungus-like organisms in the bathing sites of the river Supraśl in Podlasie Province of Poland

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Abstract. Studies on the occurrence of aquatic fungi in the bathing sites of the river Supraśl in Podlasie Province of northeastern Poland were conducted in the years 2001–2003. Some hydrochemical analyses were performed using standard methods. Bait method was used to isolate the fungi. The following species were identified: fish pathogenic fungi – *Achlya orion*, *Aphanomyces laevis*, *Dictyuchus monosporus*, *Saprolegnia ferax*, *S. monoica*, and *S. parasitica*; human pathogenic fungi – *Aspergillus candidus*, *Candida albicans*, *Lagenidium m humanum*, *Penicillium mycetomagenum*, *Rhizophyidium keratinophilum*, and *Trichosporon cutaneum*; and phytopathogenic fungi – *Achlya racemosa*, *Pythium butleri*, *P. myriotylum*, and *P. debaryanum*. Physicochemical parameters of water in the bathing sites had no important effect on the presence of fungi.

Key words: aquatic fungi, aquatic fungus-like organisms, bathing sites of rivers, hydrochemical study, Podlasie Province, Poland

Introduction

Aquatic fungi and fungus-like organisms can be found in water reservoirs where they colonize leaves, branches, stems, coastal grassy plants, and animal material fallen into water, thus contributing to the mineralization of the organic matter found in various types of water reservoirs. By exploiting vegetation and animals as the source of energy and carbon, they are involved in water purification processes (Batko 1975; Müller & Loeffler 1987). Some of them act as parasites of plants, animals, and humans. Others, which function as saprobionts, in favourable conditions acquire pathogenic properties, and may be a potential source of infection (Kowszyk-Gindifer & Sobiczewski 1986). The species composition of fungi and fungus-like organisms depends on many environmental factors, incl. physical and chemical parameters of the water. These water organisms together with bacteria decompose the organic compounds and have an important function for the matter cycle in the water environment.

The main aim of the present study was to establish the diversity of micromycetes found in bathing sites of the river

Supraśl in Podlasie Province of northeastern Poland, to determine or exclude potential etiological factors of mycotic infections in humans and animals, and to demonstrate the effect of physico-chemical factors on the growth of aquatic fungi.

Material and Methods

The study on the occurrence of aquatic fungi in the bathing sites of the river Supraśl located in Gródek, Supraśl, Wasilków, and Jurowce was conducted in the years 2001–2003 (Fig. 1).

The river Supraśl is a right-side tributary of the river Narew, 93.8 km long with the catchment area of 1844.4 km². The Prof. Witold Sławiński Landscape Park of the Knyszynski Forest is situated in its catchment. The reservoir in the village of Gródek has a capacity 116 thousand m³ and was created in process water lifting on 68th km upper course. The river cleanliness on this section is proved to be at the third degree (Kędzierzawski 2002). The bathing sites in Supraśl town on Supraśl River occurs on 37th km, in Wasilków town on 20th km, and Jurowce village on 16th km middle course. The water

Fig. 1. Bathing sites of the river Supraśl in Podlasie Province of northeastern Poland

cleanliness of these bathing sites is proved to be at the second degree. The watering places principally created for recreation are designed for living population in Białystok agglomeration which has 300 thousand inhabitants, and neighbouring localities (Kędzierzawski 2002).

Two water samples per year, in spring and autumn, were collected from each site during the period 2001-2003. Bait method was used to isolate the fungi. Small fragments of substrates of plant or animal origin were placed in water samples. The following baits were used: hemp seeds (*Cannabis sativa*), crucian carp spawn (*Carassius carassius*), and grass snake skin (*Natrix natrix*). Sterilized baits were placed in one-litre containers and poured with the river water. The containers were covered with glass plates to protect the water, at least partly, from bacterial penetration. The samples were stored in the laboratory for four weeks at a temperature approximating that of the Supraśl river water in the respective month. At that time lighting and warming were regulated. Microscopically identified mycelia were transferred to sterilized Petry plates containing distilled water. The baits were observed under a light microscope (100× and 400×) every day starting from the third day of the culture. Several microscopic preparations were made from each sample. At the same time, the respective developmental stages of fungi were determined using an

ocular micrometer. The identification of fungi involved such morphological features as shape and size of hyphae, shape of sporangium and spores, and the structure of oogonium, oospores, and antheridium (zoosporic aquatic fungi and oomycetes), mycelium and conidia (anamorphic fungi). The fungi were identified according to the publications of Waterhouse (1968), Bedenek (1972), Batko (1975), Fassatióvá (1983), Kowszyk-Gindifer & Sobiczewski (1986), Seymour & Fuller (1987), Dick (1990), Pystina (1998), and Zaremba & Borowski (2001).

Water samples used for physico-chemical and mycological analyses were collected in the same time in the two seasons, spring and autumn of 2001-2003, approximately 0.20 m from under water with a Ruttner's apparatus (capacity of 2.0 dm³). Hydrochemical analysis performed in the laboratory referred to temperature, pH, sulphates, ammonium nitrogen, nitrite nitrogen, nitrate nitrogen, phosphates, and chlorides. Physico-chemical examinations were conducted using standard methods used in Poland according to Greenberg *et al.* (1992) and Dojlido (1995).

Results

The hydrochemical analysis revealed that the water of the river Supraśl in the watering place Gródek had the highest content of sulphates and in Supraśl sulphates and chlorides, whereas the water of the river in watering places Wasilków and Jurowce had the lowest values for sulphates (Tab. 1). In each observing season, spring and autumn, significant differences in the species composition of fungi and fungus-like organisms, as well as in the physico-chemical parameters on studied watering places of Supraśl River were not proved.

During the three-year period of the present study on the occurrence of fungi and fungus-like organisms in the water of bathing sites of the River Supraśl in Podlasie Province 61 aquatic and soil organisms of anamorphic Ascomycetes, anamorphic Basidiomycetes, Chytridiomycetes, Oomycetes, Plasmodiophoromycetes, and Zygomycetes were found (Tab. 2). Most species were identified in Wasilków (36), the fewest in Gródek. The oomycetes included some freshwater fish parasites, namely *Achlya orion*, *Aphanomyces laevis*, *Dictyuchus monosporus*, *Saprolegnia ferax*, *S. monoica*, and *S. parasitica*. Species, which can act as human parasites were also identified, including *Aspergillus candidus*, *Candida albicans*, *Lagenidium humanum*, *Penicillium mycetomagenum*, *Rhizophydium keratinophilum*, and *Trichosporon cutaneum*. Other species belonged to saprobes on plant material: *Achlya americana*, *A. colorata* (Fig. 2), *A. racemosa*, *Gonopodya polymorpha*, *Karlingia rosea*, *Nowakowskiella elegans*, *Pythium debaryanum*, *Pythiopsis cymosa*, *Rhizidium americanum*, and *Pythiogeton utrifforme*, of which some were phytopathogenic: *Achlya racemosa*, *Phytophthora gonapodyoides*, *Pythium butleri*, *P. myriotylum*, and *P. debaryanum*. Moreover, *Leptomitius lacteus* (Fig. 3), which is typical of polluted waters, was observed.

Discussion

Fungi and fungus-like organisms show a high capacity for adaptation to the environmental conditions, and are therefore widely spread in nature. They can be found in water, soil and air, being a source of infection both for plants, animals, and humans.

The aquatic fungi and fungus-like organisms constitute an etiological factor of mycotic infections in fish, thus being the cause of considerable losses in hatcheries, pond, lake and river fish farms. Mycelia grow on mechanically damaged fish tissues or may appear on spawn. A mycotic infection, fish thrush saprolegniosis is induced by the aquatic oomycetes *Saprolegnia ferax*, *S. mixta*, *S. monoica*, *S. parasitica*, *Achlya orion*, *Dictyuchus monosporus*, and *Aphanomyces laevis* (Dudka *et al.* 1989; Czczuga & Kiziewicz 1999; Czczuga & Godlewska 2001; Czczuga *et al.* 2002; Kiziewicz & Czczuga 2003a).

The occurrence of fungi and fungus-like organisms in water reservoirs is of great importance for sanitary and epidemiological reasons, as some of the fungi are pathogenic to humans. Man lives in a close contact with fungi throughout life. Fungi and fungus-like organisms regarded as important etiological factors of mycotic infections are identified in fresh and salt waters. The most commonly encountered fungi in various ecosystems include such pathogenic species as *Aspergillus candidus*, *Candida albicans*, *Penicillium mycetomagenum*, and *Trichosporon cutaneum*. *Candida albicans* and *Trichosporon cutaneum* induce mycotic infections of skin, circulation systems, and organs (Dynowska 1997; Ulfig 1996; Rózga *et al.* 1999; Kiziewicz & Czczuga 2001).

Saprobic fungi and fungus-like organisms involved in decomposition of keratin of dead organic matter of animal origin and found to grow on human and animal skin, hair, and on animal feathers, horns and hoof fragments include such as *Catenophlyctis variabilis*, *Lagenidium humanum*, and *Rhizophyidium keratinophilum* (Batko 1975). These potentially pathogenic species are dangerous to man. Pathogenic

keratinophilic fungi and fungus-like organisms have been observed in various water reservoirs by Both & Barrett (1971), Czczuga (1994), Czczuga & Muszyńska (1994, 2001), Ulfig (1995, 1996, 1998), Rózga *et al.* (1999), Kiziewicz & Czczuga (2001, 2002).

Predatory fungi, to which *Zoophagus insidians* belongs, are saprobionts at conditions of a good nutrient level. Being short of nitrogen, they become predatory (Czczuga 1993; Barron 2003).

Oomycetes and chytrids can be parasites of protozoans, amphibians, rotifers and crustaceans, e.g. *Cateneria anguillulae* is a parasite of amphibians, rotifers, and small crustaceans, *Aphanomyces astaci* is a parasite of crayfish, *A. laevis* – a parasite of algae and crayfish, and *Myzocyttium microsporium* – a parasite of rotifers and pollen (Batko 1975).

Members of the genus *Aphanomyces* grow on aquatic plants and animals, while *Aphanomyces irregularis*, *Rhizidiomyces apophysatus*, *Olpidiopsis achlyae*, *O. aphanomycis*, *O. saprolegniae*, *O. varians*, *O. vexans*, and *Woronina polycystis* are parasites on the oomycetous genera *Achlya*, *Aphanomyces*, and *Saprolegnia*. They inhabit the hyphae, but can be also found inside and outside the oogonium of aquatic fungi (Batko 1975; Czczuga & Mazalska 2000).

Oomycetes and fungi can cause diseases of plants. Their spores infect plants most frequently, perforating the tissue that covers stems, leaves, fruits, and roots. Aquatic and soil environments play a significant part in the process of mycotic infections. Fungi grow on dead remnants of plants and as saprotrophs are capable of breaking down cellulose. Mycelia frequently appear on seeds, fruits, flower petals, leaves, twigs and other elements of plants.

Examples of saprotrophs are: *Achlya americana*, *A. colorata*, *Gonopodya polymorpha*, *Karlingia rosea*, *Nowakowskiella elegans*, *Pythium debaryanum*, *Pythiopsis cymosa*, *Rhizidium americanum*, *Phytophthora gonapodoides*, and *Pythiogeton utriforme*. Phytopathogenic oomycetes include: *Achlya racemosa* – a rice parasite, *Aphanomyces phycophilus* – an alga parasite, *Phytophthora gonapodoides* – a potato bulb parasite, *Pythium butleri* – a

Table 1. Physico- chemical parameters of water from the particular bathing sites of the river Supraśl (mean from 6 samples)

Specification	Watering places			
	Gródek	Supraśl	Wasilków	Jurowce
Temperature (°C)	11.5	12.0	13.5	13.0
pH	6.67	7.82	7.67	7.90
N-NH ₄ (mg dm ³)	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040
N-NO ₂ (mg dm ³)	0.013	0.021	0.015	0.017
N-NO ₃ (mg dm ³)	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200
P-PO ₄ (mg dm ³)	0.300	0.400	0.400	0.600
Chlorides (mg dm ³)	7.00	19.00	7.00	5.00
Sulphates (mg dm ³)	21.00	29.00	13.00	13.00

Table 2. Fungi and fungus-like organisms found in the particular bathing sites of the river Supraśl

Taxa	Site			
	Gródek	Supraśl	Wasilków	Jurowce
PROTOZOA				
Plasmodiophoromycetes				
Plasmodiophorales				
<i>Woronina polycystis</i> Cornu			×	
CHROMISTA				
Oomycetes				
Leptomitales				
<i>Apodachlya pyrifera</i> Zopf		×		
<i>Leptomitus lacteus</i> (Roth) Agardh		×	×	
Olpidiopsidales				
<i>Olpidiopsis achlyae</i> McLarty	×		×	×
<i>O. aphanomycis</i> Cornu			×	×
<i>O. saprolegniae</i> (Braun) Cornu	×			×
Pythiales				
<i>Lagenidium humanum</i> Karling		×	×	
<i>L. marchalianum</i> De Wild.	×			
<i>Myzocytyum microsporium</i> (Karling) Sparrow				×
<i>Phytophthora gonapodyides</i> (H.E. Petersen) Buisman		×		×
<i>Pythiogeton utrifforme</i> Minden			×	×
<i>Pythium aquatile</i> Höhnk			×	
<i>P. butleri</i> Subraman.		×		
<i>P. catenulatum</i> V.D. Matthews			×	
<i>P. debaryanum</i> R. Hesse	×	×		×
<i>P. gracile</i> Schenk	×	×	×	
<i>P. inflatum</i> V.D. Matthews			×	×
<i>P. myriotylum</i> Drechsler				×
<i>P. rostratum</i> E.J. Butler			×	
Saprolegniales				
<i>Achlya americana</i> Humphrey	×		×	×
<i>A. apiculata</i> de Bary	×			×
<i>A. caroliniana</i> Coker			×	
<i>A. colorata</i> Pringsh.			×	
<i>A. debaryana</i> Humphrey		×	×	
<i>A. dubia</i> Coker		×	×	
<i>A. klebsiana</i> Pieters	×		×	×
<i>A. orion</i> Coker & Couch				×
<i>A. polyandra</i> Hildebr.	×		×	×
<i>A. racemosa</i> Hildebr.				×
<i>A. treleaseana</i> (Humphrey) Kauffman		×	×	×
<i>Aphanomyces astaci</i> Schikora	×		×	
<i>A. irregularis</i> W.W. Scott	×	×	×	

Table 2. (continued)

Taxa	Site			
	Gródek	Supraśl	Wasilków	Jurowce
<i>A. laevis</i> de Bary	×	×	×	×
<i>A. parasiticus</i> Coker		×	×	
<i>A. phycophilus</i> de Bary			×	×
<i>A. stellatus</i> de Bary		×	×	
<i>Aplanes androgynus</i> (W.A. Archer) Humphrey	×			
<i>Cladolegnia eccentrica</i> (Coker) Johannes	×			
<i>Dictyuchus monosporus</i> Leitg.	×	×		×
<i>Leptolegnia caudata</i> de Bary			×	×
<i>Pythiopsis cymosa</i> de Bary		×		×
<i>Saprolegnia delica</i> Coker	×	×		×
<i>S. ferax</i> (Gruith.) Thur.	×	×	×	×
<i>S. mixta</i> de Bary		×		
<i>S. monoica</i> Pringsh.				×
<i>S. parasitica</i> Coker	×	×	×	×
<i>S. unispora</i> (Coker & Couch) R.L. Szym.	×	×		×
<i>Thraustotheca clavata</i> (de Bary) Humphrey		×		
FUNGI				
Chytridiomycetes				
Blastocladales				
<i>Blastocladiopsis parva</i> (Whiffen) Sparrow	×		×	×
<i>Catenaria anguillulae</i> Sorokin	×			×
<i>Catenophlyctis variabilis</i> (Karling) Karling	×	×	×	×
Chytridiales				
<i>Chytridium xylophilum</i> Cornu				×
<i>Chytrium hyalinus</i> Karling			×	×
<i>Phlyctochytrium aureliae</i> Ajello		×	×	
<i>Polyphagus euglenae</i> Nowak.	×			
<i>Rhizophydium keratinophyllum</i> Karling		×		×
Zygomycetes				
Zoopagales				
<i>Zoopagus insidians</i> Sommerst.			×	
Anamorphic Ascomycetes				
<i>Aspergillus candidus</i> Link			×	
<i>Candida albicans</i> (C.P. Robin) Berkhout	×	×	×	
<i>Penicillium mycetomagenum</i> Mantelli & Negri	×			
Anamorphic Basidiomycetes				
<i>Trichosporon cutaneum</i> (Beurm., Gougerot & Vaucher) N. Ota			×	×
Total number	25	26	36	33

Fig. 2. *Achlya colorata* – hyphae from oogonia (in the bathing sites of the river Supraśl in Podlasie Province of northeastern Poland)

Fig. 3. *Leptomitus lacteus* – hyphae from sporangium (in the bathing sites of the river Supraśl in Podlasie Province of northeastern Poland)

parasite of tobacco and potatoes, *Pythium myriotylum* and *P. debaryanum* – soil pathogens that induce decay of cotton, pea, cabbage, tobacco, and sugar beet (Batko 1975).

Leptomitus lacteus, a nitrophilic species, is a typical indicator of polluted waters (Batko 1975). This taxon can be pathogenic and is frequently encountered in polluted reservoirs, its presence allowing detection of domestic sewage inflow. It has been observed on the spawn of freshwater fish in lakes, rivers, and ponds (Suzuki 1960; Scott & O'Bier 1962; Stpiczyńska-Tober 1965; Staniak 1971; Willoughby & Roberts 1991; Czczuga *et al.* 1995; Czczuga & Muszyńska 1996). *Leptomitus lacteus* was found in the water of the bathing sites in Wasilków and Gródek which marked the highest content of nitrates and sulphates.

The physico-chemical analysis of water revealed the highest content of sulphates and nitrates in the bathing site in

Gródek and the highest level of nitrates in Wasilków. Nitrogen and sulphur, in combination with oxygen, hydrogen and carbon are the chemical parameters, building up the biomass and as components of proteins and enzymes are involved in metabolic conversion. In water, they undergo permanent transformations in which protein-decomposing bacteria and fungi are engaged. In the waters polluted with municipal sewage the content of biogenic substances increases, thus promoting the growth of aquatic fungi (Greenberg *et al.* 1992; Dojlido 1995).

Significant difference between species composition of fungi and fungus-like organisms on studied bathing sites of Supraśl River in the individual studied seasons, spring and autumn in 2001-2003, was not proved. Any changes of the physico-chemical parameters of the studied water were also not established.

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